

Interview

Introduction

Thanks for taking the time to meet with me today. I'm doing a study on the practice and process of data analytics, particularly through the baseball analytics community. First, I want to ask a few questions about your background in analytics, and then we'll discuss your current experience.

Do you mind if I record this discussion so that I can review it later?

[Assuming yes] Okay, with your permission, I am now recording the audio of the discussion.

First, how long have you been programming in any capacity?

How long have you been involved in the analytics community?

Have you had professional experience in either programming or analytics?

[If so] What were your job title and responsibilities?

Learning and Documentation Topics [Derived from Robillard]

I want to jump back to when you were learning the skills necessary for baseball analysis through software. Do you remember the primary resources you used at that time to learn about how to use software for baseball?

Do you remember why you sought out those sources in particular?

Compare those experiences to how you work today. When you go to documentation, what problems are you trying to solve?

How well does the current documentation solve it, and what problems remain with the documentation that you see?

[Optional] **Have** you yourself made any documentation or software (or both) for other people to use? **What** choices do you make in designing the instructions them so that people find them useful?

Thinking about documentation, I'm going to list a few topics for things that could appear in software documentation. I want you to specify, in a few sentences, if and when you think those topics are appropriate and helpful for documentation for baseball analytics work.

[Choose 3 to 5, according to investigator's discretion]

[Intent Documentation] How important is it for software guides to describe *why* certain choices are made in the design of interfaces or instructions, or to explain the original developer's intent in making the software work a certain way?

[Code Examples] How important is it for documentation to include examples of actual code or visual walkthroughs of an interface?

[Matching APIs with Scenarios] How important is it for documentation to describe the specific situations or questions for which you would need to use a function or feature?

[Penetrability] How important is it for documentation to let you know how the calculations are actually performed, or how the software performs behind the scenes?

[Documentation Format] How important is the format or medium of the documentation? How do you prefer it to be design, and how important is it for you that it has that specific design?

Software Engineering Topics

At this point, I want to ask about topics ranging the entire process of software development from the baseball analytics perspective. Throughout these, I want you to pay special attention to your experiences within baseball analytics as they compare to your experiences within professional engineering.

[Depending on how many interviewees I have, the number of these that I bring up is flexible.]

[Requirements elicitation and validation] Thinking about how you've traditionally worked, how do you search for and decide on which questions to ask? Or, how do you know you're asking the right question?

Throughout this process, how closely do you stick to this initial question?

[Software design according to requirements] Once you have a question in mind, how do you start the design process for the software or programs that you will use to answer the question?

[Software construction] What tools or libraries do you use to build your solutions, and why?

[Testing and verification] How much do you test the correctness of your programs according to your requirements, and how do you disperse this effort throughout the process?

[Designing for maintenance and longevity] How much thought do you give to how your software projects will have to be reused and updated in the future?

[Software Configuration Management] In achieving your programming goals, how often do you have to manage several different software systems that need coordination to work properly? When you do, how do you manage their configuration?

[Software Engineering Management] How do you manage your time and effort while programming? For example, do you outline all the tasks you'll need to complete before the end and schedule out your time beforehand, and do you monitor the time that you do use?

[Software Engineering Process] How would you describe the lifecycle of your programming projects? How do you transition between planning phases, programming phases, testing phases, and others? How much time is spent in each phase?

[Software Engineering Tools and Methods] Do you keep records of your effort, and if so, with what?

[Software quality, ethics, safety, ramifications] Do you have any other ways (other than testing) that you ensure the quality of your software?

Do you have to bear in mind other concerns, such as ethics, safety, or the consequences of your findings while developing the software? And if so, in what way?

Wrap Up

With that, we're done with the formal part of the interview. Do you have anything else you'd like to add, or any questions for me?

Now that you know what this interview is about, let me know if you know anybody else in your baseball analytics circles whom you recommend that I talk to for another perspective.

In any case, thank you for your time today.